

MCAA on Choose Europe: Attracting Global Talent to Build a Stronger ERA

MCAA Policy Paper n. 2/2025

20 May, 2025

MARIE CURIE ALUMNI ASSOCIATION

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MCAA Policy Papers: MCAA Policy Paper n. 2/2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15462203](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15462203)

Published on 20 May, 2025

by the Marie Curie Alumni Association,

Avenue des Arts 24, B-1000 Brussels, Belgium

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Cite as:

Marie Curie Alumni Association (2025, 20 May). *MCAA on "Choose Europe": Attracting Global Talent to Build a Stronger ERA*. MCAA Policy Papers, n. 2/2025. Brussels. Marie Curie Alumni Association.

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About the Marie Curie Alumni Association

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network with 22,000+ members from over 150 countries, open to any past or present beneficiaries of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), not restricted to researchers, but including their supervisors and MSCA project managers. The MCAA aims to connect the MSCA community, supporting career development initiatives for MCAA members and advocating for research and researchers.

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Background

On 5 May 2025, the President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen, [delivered a significant and forward-looking speech at the Choose Europe for Science event](#) held at the Sorbonne University in Paris, alongside the President of France Emmanuel Macron. At the event, President von der Leyen presented the first elements of the new Choose Europe initiative. Initially proposed in the Heitor report as an [initiative under the MSCA programme](#) to attract and retain outstanding young researchers in Europe, the version presented by President von der Leyen has evolved in scale and ambition, covering several actions and programmes beyond the MSCA.

MCAA on Choose Europe: Attracting Global Talent to Build a Stronger ERA

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) strongly supports the Choose Europe initiative, reaffirming Europe's commitment to research, innovation, and international collaboration. President von der Leyen's strong emphasis on freedom of scientific research and openness resonates deeply with the MCAA's core values and long-standing advocacy. Considering the growing global threats to academic freedom and the fundamental rights of researchers, the European Commission reaffirming its commitment to these principles is especially timely. The MCAA also welcomes the announcement of a future European Research Area Act to enshrine academic freedom in EU legislation. This initiative echoes the "fifth freedom" highlighted in the [Letta report](#).

The MCAA commends the President's explicit acknowledgement of diversity as a global asset and the lifeblood of science. This aligns with [the MCAA's recommendations for the future of the MSCA under FP10](#), where the MCAA calls for a more inclusive and equitable research environment.

Furthermore, the MCAA commends the reinforced focus on research careers and mobility, including President von der Leyen's commitment to speeding up visa and entry procedures for researchers. These issues are consistently raised by the MCAA's members and featured in the FP10 recommendations, where the MCAA calls for supportive frameworks to reduce barriers for international talent. To address these challenges and fully leverage the potential of international researchers, the MCAA strongly recommends that Member States implement a dedicated Scientific Visa category for researchers. This emphasis also aligns with the MCAA and the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc)'s [Declaration on Sustainable Researcher Careers](#), which advocates for stable, attractive, and inclusive research career pathways across Europe. The MCAA

encourages the European Commission to embed these frameworks into the Choose Europe initiative, ensuring that Europe is not only a magnet for talent but also a place where researchers can thrive in the long term.

The MCAA highly welcomes the announcement of a €500 million package for 2025–2027 to attract and support researchers. This, together with the goal of reaching 3% of GDP investment in research and development (R&D) by 2030 and the pledge to propose ambitious new research and innovation funding under the next Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), reflects an encouraging step toward strengthening Europe’s research and innovation ecosystem. This vision aligns closely with the goals set in the [Heitor report](#) and has been consistently echoed in recent statements such as [the joint report by various research organisations on the need for much more MSCA](#), [the response to the Horizon Europe Interim Evaluation Report by Eurodoc and the MCAA](#), [the Warsaw Declaration](#), [the European Parliament \(EP\) Resolution](#), and [the joint statement by the European Research Council \(ERC\) and the European Innovation Council \(EIC\)](#). In its [most recent position](#), the MCAA has emphasised that the next MFF must underline the call for a fully-fledged FP10 with an ambitious and ring-fenced budget dedicated solely to research and innovation. This funding must safeguard the independence and impact of programmes like the MSCA and the ERC, cornerstones of Europe’s scientific leadership and talent attraction.

At the same time, the MCAA notes concerns about certain aspects of the evolving framing of Choose Europe, particularly the potential expansion of the MSCA programme to include incentives on top-down selected topics. The MSCA programme has long thrived on the fundamental principle of a bottom-up approach, empowering researchers to initiate projects based on their own innovative ideas across all fields. This model has been instrumental in fostering ground-breaking discoveries and attracting top talent to Europe. This model, unique in its flexibility, openness across disciplines, and commitment to excellence through mobility, is one of Europe’s most effective tools for building human

capital in research and innovation. The MCAA therefore underscores the importance of maintaining the **bottom-up, independent, inclusive, and researcher-centred** nature of the MSCA.

As the Choose Europe initiative evolves, the MCAA stands ready to contribute actively through its global community of researchers, policy expertise, and role as an ambassador of European science. The MCAA urges the European Commission to ensure that this initiative builds on the full potential of the MSCA and the ERC, reinforcing a balanced, inclusive, and sustainable European Research Area. By championing diversity, mobility, a bottom-up approach, and academic freedom, and securing robust and targeted investment in research careers, Europe can become the destination of choice for the next generation of scientific talent. The MCAA looks forward to working with all stakeholders to help make this vision a reality.

Acknowledgments

**Funded by
the European Union**

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